

**DELIVERABLE D5.3 –
Dissemination, Exploitation,
Communication Plan – V2**

Project Acronym	COLOSSE
Project Full Name	Central European Platform for Plasma-Enabled Surface Engineering
Grant Agreement No.	101158464
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-04
Type of action	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Project starting date	1 April 2024
Project duration	36 months
Deliverable number	D5.3
Deliverable name	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan – V2
Work Package	WP5
Type	R – Document, report
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Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Due Date	June 2025
Date	30. 06. 2025
Version	2.0

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101158464. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Abbreviations

CENAM	– Centre for Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials
CEPLANT	– R&D centre for plasma and nanotechnology surface modifications
CU	– Comenius University
ERDF	– European Regional Development Fund
EU	– European Union
FAS	– Faculty of Applied Sciences
FMPI	– Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics
FP	– Framework programme
GA	– Grant agreement
HE	– Horizon Europe
HR	– Human resources
ICMCTF	– International Conference on Metallurgical Coatings and Thin Films
INPLAS	– Competence Network Industrial Plasma Surface Technology e.V.
KETs	– Key enabling technologies
KPIs	– Key performance indicators
MU	– Masaryk University
NTIS	– New Technologies for the Information Society – European centre of excellence
PSE	– Plasma Surface Engineering
R&D	– Research and development
R&I	– Research and innovation
RMA	– Research managers and administrators
UWB	– University of West Bohemia in Pilsen
WP	– Work package

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Executive summary

This document provides an updated detailed plan for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the activities carried out in the COLOSSE project. The communication strategy describes the objectives, identifies target groups and strategic activities, and links them to COLOSSE's key performance indicators. The document also presents communication tools and channels for capturing target groups. The document presents the website, connections to social networks, and the press in this context. The plan defines the visual identity in the form of the project logo, presentation templates, and a detailed graphic manual. The dissemination and exploitation strategy presents suitable pathways for delivering key messages related to the COLOSSE project to target groups. The document proposes indicators for monitoring impact in individual communication channels. Finally, the plan presents ways of using the outputs achieved in the COLOSSE project in relation to intellectual property.

Key words

COLOSSE, dissemination, exploitation, communication, industry, academia, citizens, visual identity, website, social media, graphic manual, impact

Summary of key updates

This second version of the document incorporates a few adjustments that are based on the experience gained during the first nine-month long of its implementation. The key updates include: preparation of a non-binding internal schedule of dissemination opportunities, update and refinement of communication channels and creation of new visual materials for dissemination purposes, revision of the list of academic recruitment portals, replacement of the semi-annual newsletter with a more flexible and continuous publication of news on the project website, and development of perspective pathways to impact.

1 Introduction

The goal of COLOSSE is to increase the participation of Czech and Slovak plasma-enabled surface engineering R&I centres in Horizon Europe and future EU Framework Programmes for R&I. The project connects three institutions: Masaryk University in Brno, the University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, and Comenius University in Bratislava.

To achieve the goal, we will focus on 4 specific objectives:

- Strengthen the connections of COLOSSE centres to world-leading R&I centres
- Build conditions that will enable internationalization of human resources
- Develop skill-set that enables interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration and facilitates creativity
- Enable sustainability of the COLOSSE partnership through synergic use ERDF and HE/FP resources

The three centres have joined together to promote our publicity and visibility on the European R&D field map. Together, we have already extended good research practices by recruiting new post-doc staff from abroad, organizing hard- and soft-skills training, and presenting our research activities at European R&D centres, conferences, and trade fairs. We also plan to organize two PhD retreat conferences with international overlap for our early-stage researchers and doctoral students.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan objectives are:

- Ensure visibility of the Project activities and results within the consortium organisations
- Ensure visibility of the Project activities and results beyond the consortium
- Increase the visibility of COLOSSE technology inventory and collaboration offer across industry and academia in Europe and beyond
- Communicate the potential applications and innovations enabled by plasma-enhanced surface engineering to a broader audience
- Engage citizens by communicating information on technological advances in a clear and accessible way and by highlighting the societal impact and importance of publicly funded research

Communication management

The communication team is composed by the leader from CU who coordinates the communication actions and takes care of the implementation of the activities, and representatives from each partner. For the second half of the project, the communication team will prepare an internal, non-binding schedule of upcoming trade fairs, technology-oriented events, and citizen-focused activities. This internal

document will serve as a reference list of potential opportunities, from which the consortium can select relevant events to participate in based on interest, availability, and strategic relevance.

The dissemination and communication strategy of COLOSSE has two main dimensions:

- External, it is guided to a large extent by the internationalization strategy developed under WP1 but will also be relevant when piloting postdoctoral career scheme under WP2.
- Internal, where we see the need to emphasize project communication towards the staff of COLOSSE centres, researchers and RMAs of COLOSSE centres. We need to engage researchers and RMAs from the project consortium to proactively reach for the benefits presented by skill development under WP2 and project development under WP3.

2 Communication strategy

Main message for all target groups: “Plasma-enabled surface engineering is facilitating technological advancement from medicine, through environmental sustainability, to space exploration. COLOSSE is funded by the EU.”

2.1. Target groups

The main target groups of our efforts are:

2.1.1. Industry

Segmented into companies (a) working on plasma technologies and (b) using plasma technologies to enhance their products in other sectors. Thanks to COLOSSE, our skills and technologies will be known and available more broadly to companies outside of Czechia and Slovakia. This, however, will also be a major benefit for our local and regional partner companies, because they may also be taken aboard in international projects along with the COLOSSE centres, and thus enhance their own networks.

2.1.2. Academia

(a) Researchers from outside of Czechia and Slovakia will be able to tap into the equipment and talent pool of COLOSSE thanks to increasing internationalization. (b) Researchers of the COLOSSE centres will increase their competences through training and enhance their collaborative networks. (c) Research managers and administrators (RMA)s from the consortium will acquire skills enabling them to support HE/FP proposals and projects.

2.1.3. Citizens

They are the ultimate beneficiaries of innovation enabled by advances in surface engineering. We will seek to communicate technological advances in an understandable way to showcase what are the end-results of public funding of research and why it is an important investment for our society.

2.2. Key messages

2.2.1. Industry

- (a, b) Invite to collaborate – list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access.
- (a, b) Share research results.
- (a, b) Invite selected companies to workshops on project development.

2.2.2. Academia

- (a) Invite to collaborate – list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access.
- (a) Advertise open postdoc positions.
- (a) Invite young researchers (i.e. early stage researchers) from our strategic partners to join the events.
- (b, c) Inform about project activities and achievements.

2.2.3. Citizens

Inform about project activities and achievements.
Present training and research activities and opportunities available at the COLOSSE centres.

2.3. Communication channels

2.3.1. Project website

Actively use the dedicated [website](#) designed for the COLOSSE platform. Inform about project objectives, consortium, and planned work. Post all events and calls. Post news on achievements of the project. Dedicated section on technology inventory and collaboration offers of the COLOSSE platform. Website will be kept open for at least 3 years after the project end. The impact of the project will be highlighted continuously (e.g. HE/FP projects awarded after the end-date of COLOSSE will recognize the support of the project).

2.3.2. Local university webpages

- Masaryk University

Masaryk University: <https://www.muni.cz/en>

Faculty of Science, Masaryk University: <https://www.sci.muni.cz/en>

Physics departments at Masaryk University: <https://www.physics.muni.cz/en>

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology, SCI MUNI:

<https://www.physics.muni.cz/en/departments/dppt>

CEPLANT (R&D centre for plasma and nanotechnology surface modifications):

<https://ceplant.cz/>

- Comenius University Bratislava

Comenius University: <https://uniba.sk/en/>

Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, CU: <https://fmph.uniba.sk/en>

CENAM: <https://cenam.sk/facilities/>

- University of West Bohemia

University of West Bohemia: <https://www.zcu.cz/en/index.html>

Faculty of Applied Sciences: <https://www.fav.zcu.cz/en/>

Department of Physics: <https://www.kfy.zcu.cz/en/>

New Technologies for the Information Society (NTIS):

<https://www.ntis.zcu.cz/en/Research/New-nanostructured-thin-film-materials/index.html>

2.3.3. Social media

We will use current accounts (Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.) of COLOSSE centres and their universities, and a dedicated [LinkedIn account](#) of COLOSSE project to inform about events and achievements linking to project website. We created a Facebook page and Instagram account COLOSSE to secure the names. The accounts are not public but are ready to be used if needed.

- Facebook

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology:

<https://www.facebook.com/ustavUFTP>

FMPI CU: <https://www.facebook.com/MatFyzJeln>

UWB: <https://www.facebook.com/FAV.ZCU>

- LinkedIn

COLOSSE: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/colosse2024/>

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/86256893/>

CEPLANT: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/103788240>

UWB: <https://cz.linkedin.com/company/ntis-new-technologies-for-the-information-society>

- Instagram

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology –

https://www.instagram.com/uftp_sci_muni/

FMPI CU: <https://www.instagram.com/matfyzjein/>

UWB: <https://www.instagram.com/fav.zcu/>

Hashtags that we plan to use:

Project in general:

#COLOSSE #EuropeanCommission #HorizonEu #HorizonEurope #Synergies
#ResearchImpactEU

Personal resources:

#postdoc #PhD #scientist #researcher #physicist

Scientific:

- General: #technology #science #tech #plasma #ThinFilms #physics
#nanotechnology #MaterialsResearch #MaterialScience
- Specific coatings: #sputtering #HiPIMS #ThinFilmDeposition #magnetron
#MagnetronSputtering #pvd #VacuumCoating #coatings
- Specific analysis: #microscopy

2.3.4. Press

If relevant, press releases will be published shortly after major project milestones (e.g. the kick-off meeting, establishment of new partnership, etc.). We will also continue to address media with the opportunity to publish interviews with leading researchers or incoming postdocs from the COLOSSE centres.

2.3.5. Presentations and posters

We will actively communicate the technology offer and project activities to academia and industry, for example by including it in scientific presentations and posters at selected events.

Figure 1 QR code and a template of a slide for dissemination of the Technology offer (D5.2)

2.4. Visual identity

As part of the project, we have developed a dedicated logo that will be used consistently across all communication materials (f.e. promotional items, e-mail signature). In addition, we have also prepared templates for presentations, documents, and other outputs to ensure a cohesive visual identity (see Annex 1 Design manual).

Figure 2 COLOSSE logo in different colours

Figure 3 COLOSSE presentation template

In line with the requirements outlined in the Grant Agreement (Article 17), all materials will prominently feature the EU logo, along with a statement acknowledging the financial support from the European Union and disclaimer.

Figure 4 European flag and funding statement

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Figure 5 Disclaimer

3 Dissemination and exploitation strategy

Dissemination and exploitation activities will ensure that results will be made visible to the appropriate communities of users and practitioners who can benefit from their application.

The main target groups with key messages and dissemination channels to maximise their impact are listed below.

3.1. Target group 1a: Industry – companies developing and producing plasma-enabled surface engineering solutions

Message: COLOSSE is a reliable partner for collaboration, either in joint projects funded by public resources, or for delivery of contract research. COLOSSE produces basic research results with strong application potential in plasma sources and plasma diagnostics.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access (e.g. CEPLANT equipment is available in open access mode thanks to funding from a national large research infrastructures scheme).
- Industry networks & associations: as outlined in Section 1.2.3 of GA, we have access to a number of plasmatech- focused networks on the interface of academia and industry (INPLAS, BalticNet, Graphene Council). We will publish and spread especially the COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer, but also ad hoc relevant results, through these networks.
- Participation in conferences and technology trade fairs: we will present the infrastructure, expertise and results of COLOSSE at venues where the worlds of academia and industry meet, e.g. PSE, ICMCTF.
- Final dissemination workshop: we will hand-pick companies where we see strong collaboration potential and invite them to participate in the final workshop.
- Project development: where relevant, we will seek to involve key industrial collaborators into the development of R&I priorities selected in WP3 from the very beginning. Thus, we plan to address them with concrete outlines for future projects, including potential funding sources, and invite them to the project development workshops.

3.2. Target group 1b: Industry – companies using surface engineering to improve their products in diverse fields of industry

Message: Surface engineering solutions are an excellent tool to increase product quality and value. COLOSSE is a reliable partner for development of tailored surface engineering solutions. COLOSSE offers outstanding infrastructure to test novel surface engineering approaches.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: same as target group 1a.
- Industry networks & associations: as outlined in Section 1.2.3 of GA, we already promote our services in broadly-targeted platforms (Technology Centres for KETs). We will publish and spread especially the COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer, but also ad hoc relevant results, through such networks, and continuously seek new platforms for promotion of our facilities.
- Participation in conferences and technology trade fairs: we will continue to reach out of the innovation community focused on plasma technologies and present ourselves at events in diverse areas of manufacturing, with tailored showcase of relevant research results and infrastructure. We will continue to promote COLOSSE collaboration opportunities for automotive, electronics, optics, energy, space, or biomedical companies.
- Project development: end-users of engineered surfaces will be essential partners in consortia of newly developed projects resulting from COLOSSE activities. We identify and address relevant companies to match the R&I priorities selected for project development in WP3 in coordination with strategic academic partners. We will invite the end-user companies to project development workshops where they are essential for the core of the project concept.

3.3. Target group 2a: Academia – researchers working in fields related to plasma-enabled surface engineering outside of Czechia and Slovakia

Message: COLOSSE is a reliable partner for collaboration. COLOSSE harbours unique equipment and expertise and is ready to contribute with it to R&I projects that can benefit from plasma-enabled surface engineering. COLOSSE can deliver creative

solutions to address difficult research questions. COLOSSE provides excellent environment for research careers of researchers originating anywhere in the world, of any gender and nationality, from PhD students through postdocs towards independent principal investigators.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: same as target group Ia.
- Participation in scientific conferences: we will join the internationally leading venues of scientific knowledge exchange with presentations of research results of the COLOSSE centres. We will continue participation in conferences such as conferences organized by IUVSTA.
- Academic recruitment portals: we will advertise open doctoral, postdoc, or other positions in portals such as Euraxess
- Final dissemination workshop: we will hand-pick companies where we see strong collaboration potential and invite them to participate in the final workshop.
- Research secondments to advanced partners: especially with our strategic partners, we will continue to build trust in the competence of COLOSSE centres through direct engagement in joint research. WPI will support international mobility of researchers, who will be the envoys of our reputation.
- Young researchers' retreats: we will selectively invite young researchers (i.e. early stage researchers) from our strategic partners to join the events, and thus the early-career networks which they will then be able to carry with them as they progress to senior positions in academia and industry.
- Project development: we will continue to involve especially the strategic partners, but also other academic stakeholders based on scientific and technological needs, in project development activities of WP3. We will identify and address suitable partners individually.
- Publications in high-quality peer-review journals: While not being produced directly by project activities, the COLOSSE efforts will contribute to quality increase of scientific publications (due to working with strategic partners, development of human resources etc.). This indirect effect is still essential for improving the reputation and collaborative potential of COLOSSE centres, since they are academic institutions and cores of future projects will still mostly comprise academic institutions.

3.4. Target group 2b and 2c: Academia – researchers at the COLOSSE centres; research managers and administrators at the COLOSSE centres

Message: The COLOSSE project represents a unique opportunity to advance research careers through training on scientific and soft skills and through enhancement of networks. For research leaders: COLOSSE represents an excellent venue to diversify and strengthen funding portfolio by development of international projects.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- Project news: we will continuously publish relevant project news to inform about recent or future activities and distribute it using different channels (e.g. COLOSSE LinkedIn account).
- Direct mailing: we will keep track of relevant groups of researchers and use a mailing list encompassing those that have the highest potential to benefit from the project. This is feasible bearing in mind that the directly involved research teams are well-defined and not excessively broad. These researchers will be addressed directly with relevant training and networking opportunities.
- Internal communication platforms: being embedded in universities, the COLOSSE centres benefit from dedicated platforms enabling internal communication (e.g. MUNI Portal). We will use these platforms to spread news and opportunities of the project.

3.5. Target group 3: Citizens – general public with interest in science, including opinion leaders and policy makers that contribute to development of environment for research and innovation in Czechia, Slovakia, and Europe

Message: COLOSSE is a technological flagship contributing to our well-being. Careers in science, technology, and engineering, in the COLOSSE centres, are fascinating and should be first choice for every talented student with curious mind.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- European Researchers' Night, European Women Researchers' Day, International Day of Women and Girls in Science in February: involvement in broader set of events organized at the level of universities. Special focus on promoting science and engineering careers towards girls and women, who are underrepresented in research staff of the COLOSSE centres.

- Open days: we will actively present training and research opportunities available at the COLOSSE centres in the open day events organized by our universities and faculties.
- Popular science articles: we will publish articles on what can be achieved by plasma technologies and also simplified background on the scientific and technological principles employed in surface modifications.

4 Impact

4.1. Impact monitoring

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities will be implemented within WP5. Where the performance of our dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities is not tracked directly by the main result KPIs of the project, we introduce dedicated indicators: DEC KPIs.

DEC KPI	Target
participation in plasma technology oriented events	3
participants from industry (final dissemination workshop)	5
participation at technology-oriented events without main focus on plasma technologies	6
participations in scientific conferences	9
news posts published on the project website	2 per quarter
popular science articles	3
press articles	4
project webpage available and constantly updated	yes
logo and visual identity of the project visible on the website and in all the project materials	yes
social media: LinkedIn posts	2 per month

Table 1 Dedicated indicators

4.2. Impact pathways

To ensure that the project results bring tangible, long-term benefits to industry, academia, and society, the COLOSSE consortium has identified the following strategic impact pathways after reaching M15. These reflect the activities carried out so far and the KPIs achieved:

1. Strengthening the integration of research and innovation across the EU

COLOSSE will intensify cooperation between Czech and Slovak centres and international research leaders. This collaboration is implemented through short-term internships of early-stage researchers and PhD students at associated partners. The consortium has created a timeline for these internships to make effective use of the project's duration, enabling researchers to bring in innovative ideas that can be incorporated into the design of a joint Horizon Europe project (WP3). An increase in joint publications and conference contributions is also expected.

2. Industrial exploitation and acceleration of innovation

The COLOSSE consortium has prepared a detailed TECHNOLOGY OFFER to disseminate targeted information about analysis, measurement, and expertise opportunities for industrial partners in the field of surface engineering and beyond. The Technology Offer is available on the project website (colosse.eu) and on the websites of individual institutions and universities, including contact persons. COLOSSE experts will actively visit major trade fairs and organize one-day workshops and discussion forums, inviting potential industrial partners and directly demonstrating the opportunities listed in the Technology Offer. We consider these paths suitable for subsequent implementation of contract research and support for joint innovations in research and development, as well as support for long-term participation in Horizon Europe projects.

3. Human resources development and talent retention

The COLOSSE consortium conducted an international recruitment process for six postdoctoral positions funded by the project. A positive experience with the implementation of the COLOSSE HR Strategy—particularly in the postdoc recruitment process—has already inspired some partners to adopt a similar approach for PhD positions and even extend it to other research groups, receiving very positive feedback. These pathways have been identified as necessary to reverse brain drain and to create a more competitive and resilient research and innovation environment in Central Europe, both in the medium and long term.

4. Science communication

Public activities, popular science articles, and participation in science festivals will ensure the visibility and understanding of COLOSSE's mission among citizens. The COLOSSE consortium has identified several specific print and online platforms with significant outreach (e.g., Denník SME, Quark magazine), where research activities will be presented. Additionally, motivating high school students to pursue studies in physical sciences is seen as a promising path, via Open Days, Researchers' Night, and similar events.

Each pathway will be supported by monitoring KPIs and collecting qualitative evidence throughout the project lifecycle. These impact pathways will be reviewed and refined in the final version of the plan (M36) to ensure alignment with actual outputs and acquired insights.

5 Intellectual Property Management

The project will not generate any research results but will facilitate their creation e.g. by mobility and recruitment, and thus we will seek to ensure that the indirectly supported results adhere to principles of sound intellectual property (IP) management. First of all, on mobility, researchers supported by COLOSSE will retain their employee status to their universities, so the results they generate will be (co-) owned by their employers – MUNI, CU, or UWB. We will outline the basic principles for ownership of results in bi-lateral agreements with the secondment hosts and seek to formalize IP arrangements with our strategic partners in a coherent manner for a longer period of time. In case of joint work among COLOSSE beneficiaries, the IPR management will be guided by Consortium Agreement based on the DESCA model.

In project development activities, we will seek to enter with the participants into non-disclosure agreements (NDA), if we aim for commercially viable products. Generally, we will however seek to be as open as possible and only as closed as necessary. And given the nature of the direct project results, we foresee that it will be possible to keep a high level of openness overall. An exception may be some presentation during early-stage researchers' retreats, where researchers may openly discuss unpublished data, or training materials whether we will involve external lecturers.

6 Annexes

6.1. Design manual

Design Manual

Logo

Logo color

- R 0, G 139, B 202
C 97%, M 29%, Y 3%, K 0%
008bca

- R 236, G 0, B 140
C 0%, M 100%, Y 0%, K 0%
ec008c
- R 0, G 174, B 239
C 100%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 0%
00aeef
- R 0, G 86, B 160
C 100%, M 74%, Y 5%, K 0%
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Roll-up

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Poppins Bold

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C 0%, M 100%, Y 0%, K 0%
ec008c

Poppins Regular

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C 0%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 100%
231f20

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Poppins Bold

R 0, G 0, B 0
C 0%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 0%
ffffff

Background

R 236, G 0, B 140
C 0%, M 100%, Y 0%, K 0%
ec008c

Social networks

Instagram

Facebook

LinkedIn

T-shirt

Digital print

Screen printing